

ICCOB PA 011

**Biodiversity and the need for the conservation of endangered medicinal
plants**

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Medicinal plants form a major part of natural biodiversity throughout the globe. Medicinal plants can be described as plants comprising of natural bioactive compounds and phytochemicals that can be actively used to cure several diseases. India is a country with rich biodiversity and a strong traditional medicinal system which employs the use of locally available medicinal plants for treatment purpose however, due to the over exploitation of forests there are several medicinal plant species that have become endangered and rare. It has been estimated that in developing countries around 80% of the population is dependent on medicinal plants for their primary healthcare and with the increasing growth in the use of herbal products the need of medicinal plants for the formulations of drugs will also increase. Hence, there is a dire need for the conservation of endangered medicinal plants to protect our natural biodiversity and also to meet the ever-increasing demand for the raw material. In the present review, we emphasize on the endangered medicinal plants observed in our natural biodiversity and are used in our traditional medicinal system, the need for the conservation of endangered medicinal plants. Effective conservation strategies like *in situ* and *ex situ* conservation, education, research, and biotechnological approaches for conservation like tissue culture, micropropagation, and synthetic seeds will also be discussed in brief.

Keywords: Medicinal plants, Biodiversity, Endangered, Conservation, Healthcare.